

Please answer following peer-support related questions

6 * When you encounter a challenging task or problem related to your studies or our course exercises, who do you prefer to ask for help first?

- A coursemate
- ChatGPT or another AI tool
- A teaching assistant
- Responsible teacher/professor
- Other

7 * Why do you primarily choose to ask for help from this source?

□ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ □ H:P

8 * Please respond to the following statements about your experiences with social interaction, group work, and learning support in your studies.

- Interacting with other students is important for overcoming learning-related challenges.
- Using ChatGPT reduces my need to discuss learning-related frustrations or questions with my coursemates.
- Coding exercises, group work, and practice sessions significantly support my learning.
- Group work and shared study sessions help me feel more connected to my classmates.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
●	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
●	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
●	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
●	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please answer following course related questions and select the most suitable option.

In case you are not participating to a course select N/A option.

11 * Estimate how much time you have used per week, on the average, for the following courses. If you not participating for a course please answer N/A.

	less than 4 hours	4-8 hours	8-12 hours	12-16 hours	over 16 hours	N/A
Course names anonymized for the peer review	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					

12 * Estimate how difficult the following courses are. If you not participating for a course please answer N/A.

	Very hard	Hard	Just right	Easy	Very easy	N/A
Course names anonymized for the peer review	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					

13 * Estimate how much have you learned in the following courses.

	Nothing	Almost nothing	Something	Quite much	Very much	N/A
Course names anonymized for the peer review	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					

14 * In general when you study, how much help do you get from following people/groups.
 If there is variation between courses you can give more detailed answer in open feedback.

	No help at all	Almost no help	Some help	Quite a lot of help	A lot of help
Teachers	<input type="radio"/>				
Course assistants	<input type="radio"/>				
First year SSE students (i.e. your classmates)	<input type="radio"/>				
Older SSE students	<input type="radio"/>				
Students from other fields	<input type="radio"/>				
AI tools such as ChatGPT	<input type="radio"/>				
Some other group of people	<input type="radio"/>				

15 Open feedback for any additional comments related to previously discussed courses.

Please answer following UNIVERSITY ANONYMIZED related questions.

16 * Select the most suitable option for you

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I have participated to guild events by ANONYMIZED	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that I'm part of ANONYMIZED community	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that ANONYMIZED is good place to study	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am satisfied with the autumn semester	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

17 * In the January lecture, there could be a possibility to have a visitor lecturer. What topics would interest you (Choose max. 3):

- Technical interviews in IT: what to expect and how to prepare
- Creating an effective CV for the IT industry
- The importance of personal projects when applying for your first IT job
- Networking in IT: how to build connections and find opportunities
- Career paths in IT: from development to management and beyond
- Skills that make a difference: soft skills for IT professionals
- Learning outside the classroom: the value of open source contributions
- Understanding Agile Development: what it means to work in an agile team
- Emerging trends in IT: what first-year students should know
- I'm not interested in quest lecturer
- Some other (give your ideas in open feedback)

18 Any other comment or open feedback you would like to give.

Empty rectangular box for content.

Submit

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